

Metadata & Data Services Activities-Functions

MaDSAF v02.01

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MaDSAF

Metadata & Data Services Activities - Functions

Introduction

This working paper¹ defines a ‘super-set’ of metadata and data services’ activities and functions (MaDSAF) derived from an analysis of the common features across current requirements, standards and criteria. There are four top-level headings: digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security.

Initial work on this topic was presented at the IASSIST 2022 Conference as Information Architecture for Secure Trustworthy Data Services², which considered the suite of components necessary for an ecosystem of FAIR³ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, ReUsable) digital objects (data and metadata). A related document - FAIR Ecosystem Components⁴ - provides an infrastructure level perspective on a three-tier operational layer of digital objects, repositories and data services, and their dependency on shared registries of information. Standards, standards bodies and assessment processes/providers are the foundation for these ecosystem components.

At the UK Data Service⁵ (UKDS), Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) functions are provided by the UK Data Archive⁶ (UKDA⁷) The UKDA is certified to the CoreTrustSeal⁸, a set of sixteen TDR Requirements⁹ adhered to by over 160 global repositories and a key influence on the TRUST Principles¹⁰ (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology). UK Data Service staff are active within the CoreTrustSeal and its Assembly of Reviewers¹¹. However, data services, including the UKDS, have

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19348676>

² Information Architecture For Secure Trustworthy Data Services <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6822236>

³ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁴ FAIR Ecosystem Components <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726533>

⁵ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/about/host-organisations-and-partners/>

⁶ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

⁷ Based at the University of Essex, the UKDA is the lead partner in the UK Data Service.

⁸ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/certified-repositories/>

⁹ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2025). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2026-2028. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17660463>

¹⁰ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. et al. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

¹¹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/assembly-of-reviewers/>

responsibilities that may be wider, or requirements that are more rigorous, than those applied by TDR standards. The UKDS seeks to benchmark its activities against a wide range of relevant criteria.

This comprehensive but high-level set of activities and functions relevant to metadata and data services is intended to support strategic planning and continuous improvement. More granular and specific requirements such as FitSM¹² (applied by the UKDS technical services team) and ISO27001 for information security management (to which the UK Data Archive is certified) can be aligned with these activities and functions. The development of MaDSAF was augmented with a review¹³ of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements to assess their general applicability to wider data services beyond TDRs. The outcome was that most of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements applied to *all* data services, with only Preservation Plan (Requirement 09) and ReUse (Requirement 13) applying to a more limited set of services.

A review and crosswalk¹⁴ of characteristics, standards and requirements for repositories and data services from a variety of UK, European and International sources (listed in Appendix A: Crosswalk References) was used to generate a common ‘super-set’ of activities and functions¹⁵

Each activity or function can be augmented with more detailed subsets of locally applicable business processes and workflows. Each activity may be supported by business information artefacts (e.g. policies and procedures) and imply characteristics of the organisation or digital objects (expressed through metadata). If this information is made transparent to relevant parties it can act as evidence for assessment.

Data and metadata services may be delivered through a wide variety of organisational models and partnerships. However, to apply standards and assess outcomes it must be possible to assign responsibilities for delivering activities and functions to a defined ‘organisational entity’. The overall model can also be used to specify and manage responsibilities and where there is a need for engagement (e.g. with data users).

The table below provides a brief example of how activities and functions can be aligned with different local variables.

MaDSAF	Information Artefact	Organisation Characteristic	Digital Object Characteristic	Transparency Method	Engagement Method	Responsibility
Activity/ Function	Collections Policy	"Is Certified"	"Is FAIR"	Public Document	User Survey	Repository/ Third Party Supplier

Table 1: MaDSAF Example Augmentations

¹² ‘Federated IT Service Management’ - a European standard for delivery of IT Services cf. <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

¹³Review of CoreTrustSeal Applicability to non-Preservation (Trustworthy) Data Services <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646134>

¹⁴ Metadata & Data Services Activities & Functions (MaDSAF): Crosswalk <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779955>

¹⁵ Broadly, *activities* may be grouped into *functions* and some of these may be defined and delivered as internally or externally facing data and/or metadata *services*. This paper does not attempt to address the wide range of different interpretations of these three terms.

Since their initial release in 2023 the MaDSAF have been referenced by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Association¹⁶ Task Forces¹⁷, including those for Preservation¹⁸ and Retention¹⁹, and into the work of the sibling FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN project. The FIDELIS project has incorporated the MaDSAF into their Transparent Trustworthy Repositories Attributes Matrix (TTRAM)²⁰, which aligns the activities and functions with transparent repository information and the CoreTrustSeal Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)²¹. EDEN has mapped their 30 Core Preservation Processes (CPP) to the MaDSAF.

In version 2.0 of MaDSAF the identifiers, activity/function labels and descriptions were updated to align with the work²² of the FIDELIS project and the related public consultation. The initial version of MaDSAF included examples of “Metadata Characteristics, Information Artefacts & Evidence” which have been incorporated into the FIDELIS examples of what repository information could or should be made available (“transparent”) for different ‘trust’ contexts.

The body of this document is an overview of the MaDSAF with a brief description for each activity or function (A|F) . These descriptions are not intended to conflict with or replace the more detailed descriptions provided in the source texts, standards and criteria from which they are derived.

Key to the diagrams below:

- Data/metadata service provider (e.g. repository) boundary. Dotted line (red).
- External actor interactions. Ovals (green).
- Activities and Functions. Rounded boxes (white text on blue background).
- CoreTrustSeal and applicable to all services. Wider border (orange).
- Aligned with CoreTrustSeal and applicable to a subset of services. Wider dotted border (orange).

All information present in the diagram below and the MaDSAF-only diagram in Appendix B is also represented in the body of the text.

¹⁶ <https://eosc.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/>

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

²⁰ Kleemola, M., L'Hours, H., Parkes, O., Recker, J., Duvaud, S., van Horik, R., Alaterä, T. J., Liberante, F., Conzett, P., Kaartinen, H., Bäckman, S., Lammert, A., & Verburg, M. (2025). FIDELIS MS12 First version of TTRAM. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17157958>

²¹ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

²² L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., Parkes, O., Recker, J., Duvaud, S., van Horik, R., Alaterä, T. J., Liberante, F., Conzett, P., Kaartinen, H., Bäckman, S., & Esteves, E. (2025). FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Guide (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144141>

MaDSAF Overview with CoreTrustSeal Alignment

MaDSAF v02.01

Headings that align with the CoreTrustSeal are presented in the text e.g. **Deposit & Appraisal (R08)**. Headings that are not applicable across all repositories and data/metadata services are preceded by the text “**Exception:**”

Each Activity or Function (A|F) is grouped under Context, Digital Object Management, Organisational Infrastructure, Technology and Security.

Context

Both AF01 and AF02 are delivered via ‘Organisational Infrastructure’ but are presented separately here as they provide essential context across all Activities and Functions.

Context

AF01 Identification & Contact

Background Information & Context (R0)

Names, abbreviations and contact details for the organisation to provide reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.

AF02 Mission & Scope

Mission & Scope (R01)

Defining the purpose (or mission) of the organisation and the boundaries of activities for which the repository is responsible. Where activities involve partners or outsourced services, the organisation retains ultimate responsibility for the activities, functions and outcomes.

Provides reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.

Digital Object Management

Digital Object Management

AF03 Conceive, Create, Collect

The stages of the research data lifecycle, before data enters a repository. Working with data or metadata creators and owners can help improve quality and highlight the benefits of curation, preservation and reuse.

AF04 Deposit & Appraisal

Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

Accepting custody of digital objects from depositors, transferring responsibility to the repository. It may also include appraising offered or requested deposits to ensure they meet established criteria for acceptance.

AF05 Curation, Quality & Compliance

Quality Assurance (R10)

Ensuring digital objects reach a defined level of quality and standards compliance before they are made available for reuse.

AF06 Discovery & Identification

Discovery & Identification (R12)

Applying persistent identifiers and descriptive metadata to digital objects to support resource discovery. Providing discovery systems and making metadata available for harvesting.

AF07 Access

Determining the appropriate method of access—such as direct download or use within a secure remote environment—and facilitating user access accordingly. Access criteria are based on the characteristics of both the digital objects and the users, in alignment with rights management policies (see AF15 "Rights").

AF08 ReUse

Reuse (R13)

Making and keeping digital objects usable and understandable depends on deposit, curation, and preservation activities. Facilitating reuse depends on understanding the needs and expectations of users, including—but not limited to—identified ‘designated communities’, through ongoing external engagement (see AF20 "External Engagement"). Repositories may mediate reuse through secure remote access systems, safe rooms, or other tools that keep the digital objects fully or partially under the service provider's control.

Exception: some repositories and data services, e.g. retention/storage-only, may not take account of the needs of those reusing digital objects’ data and or metadata.

AF09 Workflows

Workflows (R11)

Processes and activities for managing, changing and maintaining digital objects and their associated data and metadata in line with legal, ethical, policy, and other standards and operating procedures (see AF23 "Legal & Ethical" and AF14 "Policy & Standards").

AF10 Preservation

Preservation Plan (R09)

Monitoring both the technology landscape (see AF29 "Technical Infrastructure") and the user community (see AF20 "External Engagement") for any changes that could impact the usability or understanding (see AF08 "Reuse") of digital objects. When necessary, preservation actions are taken—such as migrating data formats, updating metadata (e.g., revising ontologies), or emulating the environment in which the digital object is used. These actions help ensure the long-term viability and continued accessibility of the digital object.

Exception: active preservation to ensure digital objects’ data and/or metadata remain understandable and reusable for the long term is not provided by all repositories or other data/metadata services.

AF11 Provenance & Authenticity

Provenance & Authenticity (R07)

Providing information about digital objects that details their history (provenance) and ensures their authenticity. Provenance and authenticity information can be captured at the point of deposit, generated during curation and preservation processes, and shared with data or metadata users.

AF12 Support

Providing guidance and responding to requests from depositors and users around deposit and appraisal, discovery, access and re-use of data and metadata.

Organisational Infrastructure

Organisational Infrastructure

AF13 Governance

Governance & Resources (R05)

The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the entity's mission is managed and executed.

AF14 Policy & Standards

The adoption and development of policies, standards and other criteria to guide practice, aligned with governance structures (see AF13 "Governance") and operational workflows (see AF09 "Workflows"), and in compliance with the applicable legal and ethical framework (see AF23 "Legal and Ethical").

AF15 Rights

Rights Management (R02)

The management of permissions, prohibitions, and obligations governing how digital objects are accessed and used by individuals and organisations, both within and outside the repository.

AF16 Resources

Governance & Resources (R05)

The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the organisational entity's human and financial resources are obtained and managed. This includes a knowledge of and an effective deployment of human, financial and energy assets.

AF17 People & Expertise

Expertise & Guidance (R06)

The management of human resources to fulfil the mission. Includes ensuring that sufficient skills are available, internally or externally (see AF20 "External Engagement").

AF18 Third Party Dependencies

Outsourcing R0 (6) Cooperation and outsourcing to third parties, partners and host organisations

Identifying and managing third-party organisations, hosts, partners, and other actors that are essential to operations, including the delivery of data or metadata services.

AF19 Continuity of Service

Continuity of Service (R03)

Ensuring business continuity by maintaining normal operations and preparing for disruptions. This includes non-technical processes (for technical, see AF29 "Technical Infrastructure") related to the organisation, digital object management (see AF09 "Workflows"), and security (see AF30 "Security"). It also covers recovery plans for events like service interruptions and disasters. Continuity includes succession planning for the end of a service.

AF20 External Engagement

Expertise & Guidance (R06)

Organisational interaction with external parties, including individuals, partner organisations, funders, and other relevant bodies.

AF21 Release & Publishing

The processes by which the organisation creates, manages, approves, releases, updates and withdraws information artefacts (not deposited digital objects) such as publications, policies, guidelines, and other content related to the repository activities and functions. It includes publishing information that provides evidence for external assessments (see AF24 "Criteria, Assessment, Improvement") and supports external engagement (see AF20 "External Engagement").

AF22 Interoperability

The protocols and processes by which people, processes, technologies and digital objects effectively interact with others, both within and across organisational entities.

AF23 Legal & Ethical

Legal & Ethical (R04)

The legal and ethical obligations that the organisation must be aware of and adhere to.

AF24 Criteria, Assessment, Improvement

The processes used to assess compliance with standards, policies, and procedures, along with identifying actions for continuous and targeted improvement.

AF25 Analysis & Impact

The analysis of internal data and external information to verify and demonstrate that the organisation is effectively fulfilling its mission (see AF02 "Mission & Scope").

AF26 Training

Leveraging internal expertise to train data and metadata producers, owners, depositors, and users. Training can cover the entire digital object management lifecycle, from the conception of research to the reuse of data and metadata. It also includes training for internal staff, as well as for peer organisations, partners, and third parties.

AF27 Research & Development (R&D)

Projects and other activities outside current operations, routine maintenance and upgrades. This can include new approaches to data, metadata, business processes, technology, security, and research infrastructure.

Technology

Technology

AF28 Storage & Integrity

Storage & Integrity (R14)

The methods used to store and replicate digital objects' data and metadata, including the validation of replicated copies and the restoration of data from backups in case of errors.

AF29 Technical Infrastructure

Technical Infrastructure (R15)

The comprehensive provision of hardware, software, and IT service management to support the organisation's entity. Monitoring the user community technical needs and broader technical landscape to update and maintain levels of technical service (see AF08 "ReUse").

Security

Security

AF30 Security

Security (R16)

Ensuring security across the organisation's infrastructure, digital object management, and systems. Security also extends to the boundary between the repository and external entities, including users, depositors and dependencies on third parties.

Appendix A: Crosswalk References²³

COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories

Version 2 - July 19, 2022

<https://www.coar-repositories.org/files/COAR-best-practices-framework-for-repositories-Version-2-July-19-2022.pdf>

CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance

CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling: Alignment between the FAIR Principles and CoreTrustSeal 2023-25

L'Hours, Recker, Kleemola, 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7564703> which in turn references:

Desirable characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research

Guidance by the Subcommittee on Open Science of the National Science and Technology Council, May 2022

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/05-2022-Desirable-Characteristics-of-Data-Repositories.pdf>

Digital Library Federation (DLF) Levels of Born Digital Access

DLF Born Digital Access Working Group 2020-02-05

<https://osf.io/hqmy4>

DPC RAM

Version 2. 2021

<https://www.dpconline.org/docs/miscellaneous/our-work/dpc-ram/2005-dpc-ram-worksheet>

FAIRsFAIR Service Assessment Framework

Ramezani, Sara, Aalto, Tero, Gruenpeter, Morane, Herterich, Patricia, Hooft, Rob, & Koers, Hylke, 2021

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656431>

Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources

Durinx C, McEntyre J, Appel R et al. Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2017, 5(ELIXIR):2422

<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9656.2>

National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA) Levels of Preservation

Version 2, 2019

<https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>

Supplemental Information to the NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing: Selecting a Repository for Data Resulting from NIH-Supported Research

Office of The Director, National Institutes of Health, October 29, 2020

<https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-21-016.html>

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016)

<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

The TRUST Principles for digital repositories

Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. et al. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. Sci Data 7, 144 (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

²³ Metadata and Data Services Activities-Functions Crosswalk <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779955>

Appendix B: MaDSAF Overview Diagram

Diagram: MaDSAF Overview

Version History and Acknowledgements

MaDSAF major version numbers will not increment unless the body of the Activities Functions List (label and descriptions) change, or are added or removed. Other changes will be reflected with a minor version increment.

Version	Notes	Date
v02.01	No changes to the MaDSAF labels or descriptions. Updated to the UK Data Service document template with minor corrections to the text.	2026-03-31
v02.00	This second version of the MaDSAF incorporates and acknowledges the revisions derived from project activity and associated public consultation through the FIDELIS project. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676188 .	2025-12-02
v01.00	Initial release.	2023-03-01

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